

Cerebral Venous Sinus Thrombosis

A review of potential risk factors of Oral Contraceptive, Pregnancy and Puerperium

Ramona, Wimmer
Data Science for natural Science
Fachhochschule Kufstein
2010837670@stud.fh-
kufstein.ac.at

ABSTRACT

Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis (CVST) has been reported as a dangerous side effect of AstraZeneca Covid19 vaccination and brought this disease back into the spotlight. Although this disease is considered uncommon in the literature, it was already first described in 1825. CVST is rare form of a stroke, which has a broad spectrum of signs, with headache being the most common indication. Apart from the side effect of the vaccine, a literature search revealed that studies found statistical correlations between the disease and an increased risk from taking oral contraceptives or during pregnancy and the puerperium, but these were limited by the small amount of data. Diagnosis can be detected with Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), Magnetic resonance angiography (MRA) and Computed tomography (CT), but there are currently no standard treatments. Fortunately, the mortality rate is low, and a complete recovery is predicted in 80-90% of cases. It was concluded that further research is needed to address this correlation to be taken seriously.

KEYWORDS

Cerebral Venous Sinus Thrombosis, Data collection of cerebral venous Sinus Thrombosis, causes of CVST, Oral Contraceptives causes CVST, Pregnancy and Puerperium causes CVST

1 Introduction

Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis is rare cause of secondary headache that is not always easy to diagnose. There incidence is estimated to be 3-4 cases per million per year.[1]. The announcement of partially fatal cases of cerebral vein and sinus thrombosis (CVST) or also known as cerebral venous thrombosis (CVT) following vaccination with AstraZeneca's COVID 19 has led to increased awareness of this disease.[2] This disease is by no means a new phenomenon, for as early as 1825 Ribes described for the first time a clinical syndrome with progressive headache, papilledema, secondary generalized epileptic seizures, a focal neurological deficit and the development of coma in the course of the disease.[3]

Several case-control studies [4-7] and a meta-analysis [8] found a strong association between oral contraceptives and cerebral venous and sinus thrombosis. Due to data science this association may account for the change in the epidemiology of the disease in recent

decades, which until the mid-1970s affected men and women equally, becoming a disease that mainly affects women of childbearing age [4].

The aim of this review is to provide an insight into what has been discovered statistically over the years about the association of the increased risk of Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis by taking Oral Contraceptives, or a Pregnancy and Puerperium.

In this paper, the abbreviation CVST is used.

2 Method

A literature search was done in Google Scholar and medical journals PubMed using the mentioned keywords. Case reports, case series, review articles, and observational studies with relevant documentation were analyzed for this review.

3 Definition

Thrombosis is a vascular disease or disorder of the circulatory system in which a blood clot forms in a blood vessel. Thrombosis can occur in all veins, also in the brain.[8]

CVST is classified in medicine as rare form of a stroke The clots obstruct the flow of blood out of the brain, causing it to swell (cerebral oedema) and haemorrhages can form.[4]

The first diagnosis of the disease is attributed to the French physician François Ribes, who in 1825 described the case of a 45-year-old man who died after six months of severe headaches, epileptic seizures and delirium, and whose autopsy found thrombi in the sinuses and veins of the brain.[3]

The development of angiography in the second half of the 20th century made it possible to diagnose the disease in living humans, so that larger studies of the disease pattern were feasible and it became evident that many patients have milder and more variable courses of the disease.[9]

4. Causes

Often a patient has multiple risk factors. A distinction is made between Inherited and Acquired.

Factor-V-Leiden is the most common inherited thrombosis risk factor, which is a mutated form of human factor V (one of several substances that helps blood clot), which causes an increase in blood clotting. Prothrombotic is also an inherited risk factor that occurs more frequently. The genetic information of the clotting factor

prothrombin is altered. A clotting factor is a protein that plays an important role in blood clotting. The mutation causes significantly more of the clotting factor prothrombin to be present in the blood of affected patients than in healthy humans. The blood tends to clot more quickly.

Acquired causes include Brain tumors, Head trauma, Local head infection eg.

The top CVST risk factor in women is oral contraceptive use, which is associated with a 16-fold increased risk and is the sole etiologic factor in 10% of women. In an international study, 46% of 465 women with CVST were taking oral contraceptives [9].

4.1 Oral Contraceptives

A connection was discovered in one of the first case-control studies in the Netherland 1998, de Bruijn et al. [4]. They compared prospective case series of CVST (40 women) with a random sample of 2248 women as population data in the Netherland. The published result (Table1) was that 34 of 40 (85 %) women with CVST use Oral Contraceptives, versus 1.007 of 2248 (45 %) of the control women, the age-adjusted odds ratio was 13 (95% confidence interval 5 to 37). Seven of 36 patients (19%) had a prothrombotic deficiency, compared with 7% expected in the population; this represents a three- to fourfold increase in risk. In women taking oral contraceptives who also had a prothrombotic defect, the odds ratio for cerebral sinus thrombosis was approximately 30 compared with women who had neither risk factor. Despite the correlation, absolute risk of CVST was estimated to be very small.[4].

Table 1. Result of the study de Bruijn et al. Use of oral contraceptives and prothrombotic disorders

Age (years)	Proportion (%) of controls taking contraceptives	Cases		
		Proportion (%) taking contraceptives	No with factor V Leiden	No with C, S, or antithrombin deficiency
18-19	3/3 (100)	1	0	60/107 (56)
20-24	7/7 (100)	0	0	271/336 (81)
25-29	4/4 (100)	1	1	255/400 (64)
30-34	7/7 (100)	2	0	176/392 (45)
35-39	5/6 (83)	0	1	105/342 (31)
40-44	3/5 (60)	0	0	79/336 (24)
45-49	4/5 (80)	0	0	61/335 (18)
50-54	1/3 (33)	1	0	No data
Total	34/40 (85)	5*	2†	1007/2248(45)

*Data missing for four women.

†Data missing for three women.

Another case-control Martinelli et al. [5] concluded that oral contraceptives are strongly associated with CVST and increase the risk by a factor of about 20.

One meta-analyses in 2006 including eight case-control studies of CVST and Oral Contraceptives with 263 patients and 2.862 controls, the odds ratio for developing CVST was 5.59 (95% confidence interval 3.95–7.91; p 0.001) in women using Oral Contraceptives [8].

Studies also addressed CVST cases occurring during pregnancy and puerperium [10-12].

4.2 Pregnancy and Puerperium

In 1997, a large study on the connection appeared in Glasgow. This study found an incidence of pregnancy-related venous thrombosis of 3.24 per 1000 woman-years [12].

In 2008, this study was continued in the Netherland and called the "MEGA study" and included subjects from March 1999 between September 2004. This study of 285 patients a control group of 857 participations from Amersfoort, Amsterdam, Den Haag, Leiden, Rotterdam and Utrecht, also concluded that there was an increased risk of venous thrombosis during pregnancy and the puerperium, with a particularly high risk in the first 6 weeks after birth. The risk would be even higher of pregnancy-associated venous thrombosis was greatly increased in carriers of factor V Leiden [13].

5 Clinical Signs

The symptoms of cerebral venous and sinus thromboses can be very varied and often ambiguous, as well as occurring in different temporal sequences and combinations [15].

As illustrated in Table 2. Headache is reported as the most common symptoms [15].

Table 2. Symptoms of CVST [15]

Signs	Einhäupl et al. (1990) [9] (n = 71)	Cantu and Barinagarrementeria (1993) [5]		Daif et al. (1995) [7] (n = 40)	Bousser* (1998) (n = 150)
		Puerperal (n = 67)	Nonpuerperal (n = 46)		
Headache	91	88	70	82	81
Papilledema	27	40	52	80	51
Focal deficits	66	79	76	27	38
Seizures	48	60	63	10	42
Altered consciousness	56	63	59	10	30

As there are no clear proving signs, clinical diagnosis of CVST can be very difficult [15].

6 Diagnosis

The diagnosis cannot be made based on laboratory values. The determination of D-dimers, which are used for the exclusion diagnosis of deep vein thrombosis and pulmonary embolism, has not proven helpful for the diagnosis of cerebral venous and sinus thrombosis. If the D-dimers are not elevated, this does not rule out sinus vein thrombosis. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in combination with Magnetic resonance angiography (MRA) usually allows the detection of occluded venous blood vessels. But the diagnosis can also be made reliably with computed tomography (CT)[15].

Fig.1 CT without contrast substance (left), same case in MR with contrast substance (Thrombus marked by red arrow) [15]

7 Treatment

There is no standardized treatment method for CVST to date. Revascularization, which is a procedure that can restore blood flow in blocked arteries or veins, appears to be initially the therapeutic goal [14]. With appropriate therapeutic measures, complete recovery can be ensured.[15] Strupp et al [16] reported that the outcome was dependent on recanalisation (returning the blood flow to an obstructed venous segment). Six out of seven patients without recanalisation and eleven out of 33 patients with full or partial recanalisation showed neurological deficits in the long-term course [16]. The prognosis is nevertheless promising.

8 Prognosis

Fortunately, CSVST usually has a favorable prognosis. In 80-90% of cases, there is extensive recovery with functional independence recovery. Unfavorable prognostic factors include older age, male gender, severe initial neurological impairment, deep cerebral venous thrombosis, large parenchymal lesions, and underlying systemic disease such as malignancy or severe thrombophilia [6] Nevertheless, other factors should also be considered for recovery the development of anxious-depressive states is not uncommon, especially in young patients after CVST.[17]

9 Conclusion

Several published studies have already shown a statistical association of CVST with the use of Oral Contraceptives, or a Pregnancy and Puerperium. However, most studies reach their limits due to little data. In none of the studies presented here was the use of oral contraceptives discouraged although a correlation was found.

Data science has become increasingly important over the years, but the data to be studied in this often-serious disease is scarce. Due to the side effect of Covid19 vaccination with AstraZeneca, this disease, although not new, has come into considerable focus. The already existing statistical evaluations especially by gynecologists should be taken seriously to be able to detect further cases of the described correlations at an early stage. This paper is probably not the most modern kind of data science, but it shows the limits of the field in that evaluations are only possible when enough data exist. Therefore, it can be concluded that further studies are needed in this area and to further investigate this disease after 197 years when it was first described.

REFERENCES

- [1] Stam J. Cerebral venous and sinus thrombosis: incidence and causes in ischemic stroke. *Adv Neurol* 2003; 92:225–232.
- [2] Walter, Uwe; Volmer, Erik; Wittstock, Matthias; Storch, Alexander; Weber, Marc-André; Großmann, Annette (2021): Hirnvenen- und Sinusthrombose nach COVID-19-Schutzimpfung: Neurologisch-radiologisches Prozedere. In: *Der Radiologe* 61 (10), S. 923–932. DOI: 10.1007/s00117-021-00887-3
- [3] Ribes MF: Des recherches faites sur la phtebite. *Revue Médicale Française et Etrangere et Journal de clinique de l'Hotel-Dieu et de la Charite de Paris* 3: 5-41, 1825
- [4] de Bruijn SF, Stam J, Koopman MM, Vandembroucke JP; for the Cerebral Venous Sinus Thrombosis Study Group: Case-control study of risk of cerebral sinus thrombosis in oral contraceptive users and in [correction of who are] carriers of hereditary prothrombotic conditions. *BMJ* 1998;316:589–592. [Erratum, *BMJ* 1998;316:822.]
- [5] Martinelli I, Sacchi E, Landi G, Taioli E, Duca F, Mannucci PM: High risk of cerebral-vein thrombosis in carriers of a prothrombin-gene mutation and in users of oral contraceptives. *N Engl J Med* 1998;338:1793–1797.
- [6] Ferro JM, Lopes MG, Rosas MJ, Ferro MA, Fontes J: Long-term prognosis of cerebral vein and dural sinus thrombosis. Results of the VENOPORT study. *Cerebrovasc Dis* 2002; 13:272–278.
- [7] Ferro JM, Canhao P, Stam J, Bousser MG, Barinagarrementeria F; ISCVT Investigators: Prognosis of cerebral vein and dural sinus thrombosis: results of the International Study on Cerebral Vein and Dural Sinus Thrombosis (ISCVT). *Stroke* 2004;35:664–670
- [8] Dentali F, Crowther M, Ageno W: Thrombophilic abnormalities, oral contraceptives, and risk of cerebral vein thrombosis: a meta-analysis. *Blood* 2006;107:2766–2773.
- [9] Saposnik G, Barinagarrementeria F, Brown RD Jr, Bushnell CD, Cucchiara B, et al.; American Heart Association Stroke Council and the Council on Epidemiology and Prevention. Diagnosis and management of cerebral venous thrombosis: a statement for healthcare professionals from the American Heart Association/ American Stroke Association. *Stroke* 2011; 42: 1158–92
- [10] Duman T., Uluduz D., Midi I., et al. A Multicenter Study of 1144 Patients with Cerebral Venous Thrombosis: The VENOST Study. *Journal of Stroke and*
- [11] Mehraein S, Ortwein H, Busch M, Weih M, Einhaupl K, Masuhr F: Risk of recurrence of cerebral venous and sinus thrombosis during subsequent pregnancy and puerperium. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry* 2003;74:814–816.
- [12] McColl MD, Ramsay JE, Tait RC, Walker ID, McCall F, Conkie JA, Carty MJ, Greer IA. Risk factors for pregnancy associated venous thromboembolism. *Thromb Haemostasis* 1997;78:1183–8.
- [13] Pomp ER, Lenselink AM, Rosendaal FR, Doggen CJ. Pregnancy, the postpartum period and prothrombotic defects: risk of venous thrombosis in the MEGA study. *J Thromb Haemost.* 2008 Apr;6(4):632–7. doi: 10.1111/j.1538-7836.2008.02921.x. Epub 2008 Jan 31. PMID: 18248600.
- [14] M. Capecci, M. Abbattista, I. Martinelli: Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis. (Review) In: *Journal of Thrombosis and Haemostasis*. Band 16, Nr. 10, Oktober 2018, doi:10.1111/jth.14210, S. 1918–1931.
- [15] Bousser, MG. Cerebral venous thrombosis: diagnosis and management. *J Neurol* 247, 252–258 (2000). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s004150050579>
- [16] Strupp M, Covi M, Seelos K, et al. Cerebral venous thrombosis: correlation between recanalization and clinical outcome – a long-term follow-up of 40 patients. *J Neurol* 2002;249:1123–4.
- [17] Bousser MG, Ferro JM. Cerebral venous thrombosis: an update. *Lancet Neurol.* 2007 Feb;6(2):162-70. doi: 10.1016/S1474-4422(07)70029-7. PMID: 17239803.